

Chemistry of Mixed Ligand Complexes of Copper(II) involving Ketoanil and Thiourea, Ammonia or Anionic Ligands

R. K. UPADHYAY

Department of Chemistry, N. R. E. C. College, Khurja-203 131

Manuscript received 5 September 1994, revised 31 January 1996, accepted 14 May 1996

Mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} involving thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptyl-, -2-pyridine- or -2-pyrimidine-anil and thiourea, ammonia or anionic ligands, obtained either by direct reaction or by partial or complete replacement of strongly coordinated ammonia of cupric ammine complex, have been synthesised and characterised.

Novel ligation properties¹⁻³ of ketoanils in forming complexes of unusual stereochemistries and of isomeric compositions and rare exploration^{4,5} of complexes derived by partial or complete replacement of strongly coordinated ammonia, halogen, cyanide or thiocyanate by neutral organic donor molecules including ketoanils⁶, aroused our interest to synthesise a few mixed ligand complexes of Cu^{II} with thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptyl- (1), -2-pyridine- (2) or -2-pyrimidine- (3) anil and thiourea, ammonia or anionic ligands either by direct reaction of ketoanil with cupric salts or by partial or complete replacement of ammonia of cupric ammine complex by ketoanil or by ketoanil and thiourea. Most of the products are isomers of unusual octahedral geometry.

Results and Discussion

Structural formulae of the complexes are consistent with their analytical and molar conductance data. The low Λ_M values may be attributed to the large cations.

Ir bands for C=N and C-S mercaptyl appearing at 1 620 and 870, 845 cm⁻¹ in 1 are observed respectively at ca. 1 595 and 851, 810 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Lowering in frequencies of these bands and appearance of new bands at ca. 512 (M-N) and 293 cm⁻¹ (M-S) show coordination of both the groups with Cu^{II} ion. The ν_{SH} ligand band (2 320 cm⁻¹) appearing at ca. 2 322 cm⁻¹ in the complexes, indicates^{2,7} the presence of unionised SH, probably due to its intramolecular H-bonding with acyclic C=N group in the coordination zone as also suggested by Λ_M data.

The $\nu_{C=N}$, $\nu_{C=C}$ aromatic, ring breathing, ϕ C-C and C-C deformation frequencies^{2,7-9}, observed at 1 630, 1 590, 1 070, 1 040 and 980, 725, and 405 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of 2 and at 1 665, 1 575 and 1 500, 1 085, 1 065, 1 050 and 980, 720 (doublet), and 430 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of 3, have been displayed respectively at ca. 1 607, 1 581 and 1 520, 1 055, 1 008 and 965, 717 (doublet) and 410, and 1 635, 1 568, 1 023 and 965, 710, and 423 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes of 2 and 3. Considerable disturbance, lowering in frequency/disappearance or change in structure of ir peaks of both the ligands on complexation clearly show⁷⁻¹⁰ their biligancy through azo-methine and heterocyclic ring nitrogens; either two clear peaks or a

broad peak which could arise from two peaks of small frequency difference, attributed to ν_{M-N} , appeared only in complex spectra in 445-590 cm⁻¹ range support¹⁰ coordination of both nitrogen atoms with metal ion. Doublet or broad structure of one of the M-N peaks of the complexes obtained by partial substitution of ammonia by 2 and 3 could only be accounted for considering third nitrogen donor, possibly ammonia, in the coordination sphere. The free NH₂ and N-H stretching (3 140-3 550 cm⁻¹) and N-H rocking (ca. 845 cm⁻¹) vibrations of coordinated ammonia confirm its coordination. In the ir spectra of the products involving SCN₂H₄ and 2 or 3 unperturbed amine frequencies and a new low frequency band at 260-320 cm⁻¹ indicate bonding of SCN₂H₄ through sulphur. In these complexes unreduced Cu^{II} state, revealed by conductometric studies, supports coordination of SCN₂H₄ through its sulphur and indicates non-bonding of NH₂, reducing groups, which could cause reduction to Cu^I state. Carbonyl and thienyl groups of all the three ketoanils do not seem to coordinate with metal ion as their peaks appear almost at the same frequency in complexes.

To octahedral complexes of ML₂Cl₂ type, [Cu(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂Cl₂].2H₂O^b), [Cu(C₁₁H₈N₂SO)₂Cl₂].H₂O^a) and [Cu(C₁₀H₇N₃SO)₂Cl₂]^b), in which monodentate chlorine exhibits two degenerate ir-active Cu-Cl bands at ca. 318 and 378 cm⁻¹ C_{2v} (trans) symmetry could be assigned^{2,11}, whereas [Cu(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂Cl₂].2H₂O^a) and [Cu(C₁₀H₇N₃SO)₂Cl₂]^a) displaying only one ν_{Cu-Cl} band at ca. 318 cm⁻¹ are cis-isomers of C_{3v} symmetry^{2,11}. Complexes involving SCN₂H₄/NH₃ alongwith 2 or 3 exhibit one ν_{Cu-Cl} band at ca. 382 cm⁻¹ except b-isomer of NH₃ and 2 displays an additional band at 240 cm⁻¹. A new band at 415 cm⁻¹ in addition to ν_{Cu-Cl} band (365 cm⁻¹) in [Cu(C₁₁H₈N₂SO)₂(H₂O)Cl]Cl^b) may be attributed to ν_{M-O} of coordinated H₂O; this complex is very soluble in coordinating solvents like pyridine and DMSO. Cu-Br terminal stretching frequency appears at 245 cm⁻¹.

The bands at ca. 2 065, 815 and 510 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of the thiocyanato complexes corresponding to ν_{C-N} , ν_{C-S} and δ_{NCS} respectively, indicate non-bridging nitrogen coordinated and/or free SCN⁻ groups. This inference is supported by a medium intensity ν_{Cu-N} band at

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	M.p., °C	Δ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{mol}^{-1}\text{cm}^2$	μ_{eff} B.M.	$\lambda_{\text{max}} (\text{cm}^{-1})$		
					${}^2A_{1g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$	${}^2B_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$	${}^2E_g \leftarrow {}^2B_{1g}$
C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O	Brown	90	—	—	—	—	—
C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO	Brown	61	—	—	—	—	—
C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO	Violet	120	—	—	—	—	—
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O ^{a)}	Orange	190	23.8 (non)	2.14	12 121	14 705	15 873
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ Cl ₂].2H ₂ O ^{b)}	Brown	210	45.4 (non)	2.13	12 195	14 285	17 543
[Cu ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ (NCS) ₂](CNS) ₂ ^{c)}	Orange	230	158.0 (1 : 2)	1.99	17 241	18 181	18 867
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ (CNS) ₂] ^{d)}	Orange	115	36.1 (non)	2.23	13 698	15 384	16 949
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ SO ₄] ^{e)}	Orange	185	22.3 (non)	2.11	13 698	15 873	16 666
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ SO ₄] ^{d)}	Yellow	205	135.9 (1 : 2)	2.03	14 286	16 807	21 053
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ (NO ₃) ₂] ^{a)}	Yellow	195	42.1 (non)	2.18	13 072	15 152	18 868
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ^{b)}	Yellow	110**	130.7 (1 : 2)	2.01	17 544	19 417	21 277
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ Br ₂]	Brown	130	24.5 (non)	2.11	13 333	15 873	17 241
[Cu ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₃ PO ₄](OH)	Brown	120	81.2 (1 : 1)	2.06	15 151	17 241	19 607
[Cu(C ₁₂ H ₉ NS ₂ O) ₂ (CH ₃ COO) ₂]	Brown	120	34.1 (non)	2.13	14 085	15 152	16 393
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ Cl ₂].H ₂ O ^{a)}	Green	80	24.7 (non)	2.19	14 285	15 625	16 666
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ Cl(H ₂ O)]Cl ^{b)}	Yellow	140	105.4 (1 : 1)	2.18	13 513	14 184	15 625
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (NH ₃)Cl]Cl ^{a)}	Yellow	>360**	95.8 (1 : 1)	2.10	13 333	14 705	15 384
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (NH ₃)Cl]Cl ^{b)}	Brown	250	111.9 (1 : 1)	2.15	14 925	15 384	17 241
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl]Cl ^{a)}	Yellow	>360	109.6 (1 : 1)	2.16	14 925	15 625	16 393
[Cu(C ₁₁ H ₈ N ₂ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄) ₂]Cl ₂ ^{b)}	Yellow	180	154.6 (1 : 2)	2.20	12 987	13 513	15 384
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ Cl ₂] ^{a)}	Green	216	27.7 (non)	2.13	14 706	15 873	17 699
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ Cl ₂] ^{b)}	Yellow	185	25.9 (non)	2.15	14 184	15 385	19 608
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (NH ₃)Cl]Cl	Yellow	192	115.1 (1 : 1)	2.19	12 346	13 072	14 925
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄)Cl]Cl ^{a)}	Yellow	>360	110.0 (1 : 1)	2.11	12 422	13 158	14 389
[Cu(C ₁₀ H ₇ N ₃ SO) ₂ (SCN ₂ H ₄) ₂]Cl ₂ ^{b)}	Green	>360	165.1 (1 : 2)	2.15	12 048	13 158	13 889

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and N analyses.

a,b,c,d) Low R_f, high R_f, acetone insoluble and soluble components respectively. ** Colour changed.

ca. 445 cm⁻¹ along with the band of ketoanil; additional bands at 290 and 2 160 cm⁻¹ in [Cu₂(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂(NCS)₂](CNS)₂^{c)} corresponding to ν_{M-S} and bridging NCS⁻, however, reveal biligancy of NCS⁻ through nitrogen and sulphur. Ir bands of [Cu(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂SO₄]^{e)} at 975, 1 160, 1 115 and 1 080, and at 460 and 1 535 cm⁻¹ corresponding^{2,12} to ν_{S-O} and δ_{S-O} respectively, of bidentate sulphate ion and a ν_{M-O} band (doublet) at 425 cm⁻¹ suggest coordination of SO₄²⁻ ion through its oxygen(s). Nitrate complex [Cu(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂(NO₃)₂]^{a)} display four bands at 1 300, 1 020, 1 435 and 850 cm⁻¹ corresponding^{2,12} to ν_{NO_2} symmetric, ν_{NO_2} asymmetric and ρ_{NO_2} asymmetric out-of-plane respectively, only out of the expected six bands. But spectrum exhibits expected two pairs of combination bands at 1 765 and 1 740, and 2 330 and 2 205 cm⁻¹, the energy separation of the first two and last two of these bands is 25 cm⁻¹ and 125 cm⁻¹. These results and broad structure of ν_{M-N} peak of ketoanil at 520 cm⁻¹ lead us to propose monoligancy of NO₃⁻ through its nitrogen. Greater separation in ν_{C-O} asymmetric and symmetric

bands, occurring at 1 575 and 1 405 cm⁻¹ of acetato complex than that exists in the free acetate ion (1 53 cm⁻¹) indicates^{2,12} monoligancy of acetate ion; characteristic Cu-O band appears at 340 cm⁻¹ in the complex.

Magnetic moments (ca. 2.02 B.M.), close to spin-only value, and electronic spectral bands at 14 266–21 277 cm⁻¹ range of electrolytic products involving 1, and thiocyanate, sulphate, nitrate and phosphate ions, characteristic of D_{4h} symmetry^{5,13}, clearly indicate square-planar geometry of four coordinate complexes, whereas higher μ_{eff} values than spin-only values and bands at 12 048–19 608 cm⁻¹ of other complexes indicate their distorted octahedral stereochemistry^{4,5}. The broad peak structure in some instances could be accounted for considering Jahn-Teller effect involving ${}^2T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions. *Cis*- and *trans*-symmetries assigned^{5,12} to a- and b-isomers respectively, of [Cu(C₁₂H₉NS₂O)₂Cl₂].2H₂O, [Cu(C₁₁H₈N₂SO)₂(NH₃)Cl]Cl and [Cu(C₁₀H₇N₃SO)₂Cl₂] products on the basis of differences in frequencies of second and third *d-d* bands are consistent with the ir results.

Experimental

Thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-mercaptyl- and -2-pyridine-anils, precipitated almost in quantitative yields on mixing solutions containing equimolar quantities of thiophene-2-glyoxal¹⁴ and amine in ether, and thiophene-2-glyoxal-2-pyrimidineanil, obtained after refluxing equimolar quantities of reactants in alcohol and concentrating and crystallising the reaction mixture, were purified by recrystallisation from acetone or ethanol.

Cupric ammine complex, $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]\text{Cl}_2$, was prepared and purified by the reported method¹⁵. Complexes involving **1**, **2** or **3** and anionic ligands were prepared by mixing equimolar solutions of ketoanils and metal salts in $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (13 : 7, v/v) in appropriate ratio followed by refluxing for 1–2 h, concentrating and crystallising the mixture except the chloride complexes with **2** and **3** which precipitated immediately while mixing equimolar acetone solutions of the reactants. For the preparation of sulphate complex with **1** solvent medium was $\text{EtOH}-\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (1 : 1, v/v). The solids, washed successively with H_2O , Me_2CO and Et_2O , were dried in hot air-oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

The complexes resulting from partial replacement of coordinated ammonia by **1**, **2** or **3** were prepared by mixing aqueous ethanolic (60%) solutions of ligands (1 mol) with ammine complex (1 mol) in presence of NH_3 (10–20 cm^3). The solids, crystallised after mixing with an equal volume of EtOH , heating to reflux for 1–2 h and concentrating the mixtures, were washed repeatedly with H_2O containing small amount of NH_3 and finally with $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}/\text{Et}_2\text{O}$ and dried in a hot air-oven at $\sim 60^\circ$.

The complexes of **1**, **2**, or **3** and thiourea could not be prepared by replacement procedure as complete substitution of coordinated ammonia with either one or both of the ligands was found to be impossible for unknown reasons. Therefore, these complexes were prepared by mixing equimolar acetonic solutions of **2** and **3** and thiourea with cupric chloride solution in the appropriate ratio. Owing to, probably higher ligating ability of thiourea than **1**, the latter was not effective in presence of thiourea and consequently cupric thiourea complex was formed instead of expected mixed ligand complex of **1** and thiourea. Both the solids, crystallised after refluxing for 1–2 h and concentrating the mixtures, were washed successively with Me_2CO and Et_2O and dried at $\sim 60^\circ$.

Metal salts and other chemicals (B.D.H., L.R.) were used as such. The complexes were tested for their homogeneity by tlc on starch bound silica gel layers, which indicated that several of them were binary mixtures. These

mixtures were resolved in bulk by column chromatography conducted in columns of different sizes according to the quantities of samples available, containing silica gel (50–100 mesh, B.D.H.). Columns were loaded with solution of products in DMF except $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_9\text{NS}_2\text{O})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SO})_2\text{Cl}_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ in Me_2CO . With the sole exception of $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_8\text{N}_2\text{SO})_2(\text{SCN}_2\text{H}_4)_2]\text{Cl}_2$, which was resolved by $\text{Me}_2\text{CO}-\text{CHCl}_3$ (4 : 1, v/v), Me_2CO was used for all the mixtures as the developing solvent. The slow moving low R_f component was eluted with EtOH or DMF. Eluates were evaporated to dryness at 75° .

Binary products consisting of an insoluble ingredient, unresolved by column chromatography, were resolved by treating them with acetone, filtering and drying the insoluble solid and residue obtained by evaporating the filtrate at 50° in an oven.

C, H and N were determined microanalytically. Conductance of standard solutions of complexes in DMF was measured on a Toshniwal conductivity bridge using a dip-type cell. Electronic spectra of the complexes in DMF were recorded on a Beckmann DU-2 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (nujol) on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility was measured on a Gouy balance at room temperature (300 K).

References

1. R. K. UPADHYAY, V. KUMARI and V. P. SINGH, *J. Liq. Chromatogr.*, 1982, **5**, 1141.
2. R. K. UPADHYAY and A. RANI, *Acta Chim. Hung.*, 1989, **126**, 195.
3. A. K. BAJPAI, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1983
4. R. P. MISRA, B. B. MAHAPATRA and S. GURU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 515.
5. R. K. UPADHYAY, A. K. BAJPAI and K. RATHORE, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1985, **10**, 24.
6. P. P. SINGH, S. A. KHAN and M. U. KHAN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 35.
7. A. RANI, Ph.D. Thesis, Meerut University, 1985.
8. J. H. S. GREEN, W. KYNASTON and H. M. PAISLEY, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1963, **19**, 549.
9. G. ZERBI, J. OVEREND and B. GRAWFORD, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1963, **38**, 112.
10. N. S. GILL, R. H. NUTTALL, D. E. SCAIFE and D. W. A. SHARP, *J. Inorg. Chem.*, 1961, **18**, 79.
11. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
12. J. LEWIS and R. G. WILKINS, "Modern Coordination Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1964.
13. K. GOPALKRISHAN, V. CHUDASMA and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 752
14. R. K. UPADHYAY, *Chromatographia*, 1978, **11**, 197.
15. A. KIND, "Inorganic Preparations", ed. A. J. E. WELCH, Allen and Unwin, London, 1950.